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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a general motion of free asymmetrical rigid body to an absolute coordinate system is studied. The rotation component of body motion is described by using of Cardan angles. A new kind of theorem is formulated. It is called Theorem of change of generalized body impulse. New kinds of differential Lagrange equations of second order are formulated. These are called Condensed Lagrange equations. Using that theorem and those equations, the general motion of the rigid body is successfully studied. The paper is theoretical, but it gives a base for a number of applications, for example, applications in the field of body overflow in fluid area and in the field of body vibrations. Moreover, the obtained formulas are appropriate for computer numerical integrations by contemporary mathematical programs.

Key words: rigid body, general motion, generalized body impulse, condensed Lagrange equations.

1. INTRODUCTION

It was just over 229 years when, on April 5, 1788, the great Italian-French mathematician and physicist Joseph Louis Lagrange presented to the Paris Academy his famous book *Mécanique analytique*. In it, for the first time, a classical form of differential equations for the study of non-free mechanical systems with many degrees of freedom is presented. These equations are known as Lagrange equations from the second order [1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

Analytical mechanics has been developed over the years. There are many modifications to these equations, for example [6, 7, 8].

In 1857, English mathematician Arthur Cayley (1821-1895) published the treatise *A memoir on the theory of matrices* [9]. With this treatise he initiated the gradual penetration of matrices and matrix calculus in the area not only of mathematics but also in a large number of other scientific fields.

Matrices begin to be used in Mechanics relatively late. This stands after the introduction of electronics and computers [10]. They are widely used in the field of Deformable Solid Mechanics and Finite Element Method [11, 12, 13], Fluid Mechanics [14, 15], Mechatronics and Robotics [16] and others. However, many parts of Mechanics of Rigid Body are presented in classical form [17, 18]. That is valid also for Kinematics and Dynamics of the general motion of a rigid body. In the most books Mechanics is developed in scalar-vector type [19, 20].

The present article is conducted entirely in a matrix form. This approach makes it the possible two main theorems in Mechanics: Theorem of change of the quantity of motion and Theorem of change the kinetic moment, applied to an asymmetrical ideal rigid body that performs an absolute general motion, to be summarized in one single theorem. It is called Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse. Moreover, new kind of modified Lagrange equations are constructed. These equations are called Condensed Lagrange equations.

The differential equations describing the absolute general motion of asymmetrical rigid body are easily obtained using that theorem or those equations. They are composed in matrix form which is very convenient for contemporary program working with matrices, for example MatLab.

2. KINETICS CHARACTERISTICS

An asymmetric free rigid body (B) that achieves a general motion is considered. The movement of the body is counted against another body (A) conditionally assumed to be immovable. A fixed coordinate system $N\xi\eta\zeta$ is connected to it (Fig.1).

Two coordinate systems are introduced at arbitrary point O in the body (B). The first coordinate system $OXYZ$ moves translational and the second coordinate system $Oxyz$ is steadily connected to the body (B). The spherical component of the rigid body motion is described by Cardan angles ψ , θ and φ . They are very convenient to set the initial conditions and eventually for linearization of the angular rotations [13].

Fig.1: Absolute general motion of free rigid body

It is assumed that the two most important Kinematics characteristics are already known. These are the velocity of the pole O and the angular velocity of the body. They are defined by the following vectors:

$$(1) \quad \mathbf{v}_o = \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_o = \langle \dot{\xi}_o \quad \dot{\eta}_o \quad \dot{\zeta}_o \rangle^T,$$

$$(2) \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} = \begin{bmatrix} \omega_\xi \equiv \omega_x = \dot{\psi} + \dot{\phi} \cdot \sin \theta \\ \omega_\eta \equiv \omega_y = \dot{\theta} \cdot \cos \psi - \dot{\phi} \cdot \cos \theta \cdot \sin \psi \\ \omega_\zeta \equiv \omega_z = \dot{\theta} \cdot \sin \psi + \dot{\phi} \cdot \cos \theta \cdot \cos \psi \end{bmatrix}.$$

The law of body motion is set with the vector of generalized coordinates:

$$(3) \quad \mathbf{q} = \langle \xi_o \quad \eta_o \quad \zeta_o \quad \psi \quad \theta \quad \phi \rangle^T.$$

For further presentation of the theory in this paper, it is necessary to define a new vector that combines the vector velocity of the pole O and the vector angular velocity of the body. It has also a dimension 6×1 and has the following type:

$$(4) \quad \mathbf{u}_o = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_o \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_o \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$(5) \quad \mathbf{u}_o = \langle \dot{\xi}_o \quad \dot{\eta}_o \quad \dot{\zeta}_o \quad \omega_x \quad \omega_y \quad \omega_z \rangle^T.$$

The name of this new vector \mathbf{u}_o is **vector-real generalized velocity** of the body at an arbitrary chosen pole O from it.

The relationship between the vector-real generalized velocity \mathbf{u}_o and the vector generalized velocity $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ of the same body is realized by the equality:

$$(6) \quad \mathbf{u}_o = \mathbf{H} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}.$$

Using the Cardan angles, the matrix \mathbf{H} from the above formula is constructed in the following manner:

$$(7) \quad \mathbf{H} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \bar{\mathbf{H}} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$(8) \quad \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{diag} [1]_3,$$

$$(9) \quad \mathbf{0} = \mathbf{diag} [0]_3,$$

$$(10) \quad \bar{\mathbf{H}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \sin \theta \\ 0 & \cos \psi & -\cos \theta \cdot \sin \psi \\ 0 & \sin \psi & \cos \theta \cdot \cos \psi \end{bmatrix}.$$

The body mass center C is defined by the absolute radius vector \mathbf{p}_C and the relative radius vector \mathbf{r}_C , respectively:

$$(11) \quad \mathbf{p}_C = \langle \xi_C \quad \eta_C \quad \zeta_C \rangle^T,$$

$$(12) \quad \mathbf{r}_C = \langle X_C \quad Y_C \quad Z_C \rangle^T.$$

A second vector \mathbf{u}_C , which name is vector-*real* generalized velocity of the body at a chosen pole O coincides with the mass center C , is defined:

$$(13) \quad \mathbf{u}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_C \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_C \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$(14) \quad \mathbf{u}_C = \langle \xi_C \quad \eta_C \quad \zeta_C \quad \omega_x \quad \omega_y \quad \omega_z \rangle^T.$$

The free ideal rigid body that performs a general motion is considered to be homogeneous.

The mass properties of the body are defined by its mass m and by the diagonal mass matrix:

$$(15) \quad \mathbf{M} = \mathbf{diag} [m]_3.$$

The inertial properties of the body are defined by two tensors of inertia.

The first one is determined for the pole O :

$$(16) \quad \mathbf{J}_O = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{J}_X & -\bar{J}_{XY} & -\bar{J}_{XZ} \\ -\bar{J}_{YX} & \bar{J}_Y & -\bar{J}_{YZ} \\ -\bar{J}_{ZX} & -\bar{J}_{ZY} & \bar{J}_Z \end{bmatrix}.$$

The second tensor is determined for the mass center C :

$$(17) \quad \mathbf{J}_C = \begin{bmatrix} J_X & -J_{XY} & -J_{XZ} \\ -J_{YX} & J_Y & -J_{YZ} \\ -J_{ZX} & -J_{ZY} & J_Z \end{bmatrix}.$$

Due to the arbitrary choice of the pole O , a reverse symmetrical tensor of the mass static moments is also used:

$$(18) \quad \mathbf{S}_C = m \cdot \mathbf{R}_C, \quad \text{where}$$

$$(19) \quad \mathbf{R}_C = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -Z_C & Y_C \\ Z_C & 0 & -X_C \\ -Y_C & X_C & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

All the forces acting on the body are reduced for a point O to main force \mathbf{F} and a main moment \mathbf{M}_O .
The following vector is defined:

$$(20) \quad \mathbf{D}_O = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{S}_C^T \\ \mathbf{S}_C & \mathbf{J}_O \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_O \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Its name is **vector-generalized impulse** of a rigid body for the pole O .

The matrix:

$$(21) \quad \mathbf{A}_O = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{S}_C^T \\ \mathbf{S}_C & \mathbf{J}_O \end{bmatrix},$$

defines the mass and inertial properties of this asymmetric ideal rigid body when for a pole is chosen the point O .

The formula (20) in a shortened vector-matrix form is written:

$$(22) \quad \mathbf{D}_O = \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O.$$

The vector-generalized impulse of a rigid body for its mass center C is defined by the following expression:

$$(23) \quad \mathbf{D}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_C \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix}.$$

The matrix:

$$(24) \quad \mathbf{A}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix},$$

defines the mass and inertial properties of this asymmetric ideal rigid body when the pole O is chosen to coincide with the mass center C .

Formula (23) in a shortened vector-matrix form can be written:

$$(25) \quad \mathbf{D}_C = \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C.$$

Finally, the vector-generalized impulse of a rigid body for the immovable pole N is introduced. This vector is defined by the formulas:

$$(26) \quad \mathbf{D}_N = \mathbf{D}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{D}_C, \quad \text{where}$$

$$(27) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$(28) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\zeta_O & \eta_O \\ \zeta_O & 0 & -\xi_O \\ -\eta_O & \xi_O & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Formulas (22) and (25) in equation (26) are substituted and the following equation is obtained:

$$(29) \quad \mathbf{D}_N = \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C.$$

The kinetic energy of this asymmetrical rigid body has the type:

$$(30) \quad E_k = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle \mathbf{v}_O \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{S}_C^T \\ \mathbf{S}_C & \mathbf{J}_O \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_O \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Formula (30) could be written in a shortened vector-matrix form:

$$(31) \quad E_k = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \mathbf{u}_O^T \cdot \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O.$$

If the pole O coincides with the mass center C , the kinetic energy will be determined by König Theorem:

$$(32) \quad E_k = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \langle \mathbf{v}_C \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle^T \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_C \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Formula (32) could be written in a shortened vector-matrix form:

$$(33) \quad E_k = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \mathbf{u}_C^T \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C.$$

The **vector-real generalized force** of this rigid body at pole O is defined:

$$(34) \quad \mathbf{Q}_O = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{M}_O \end{bmatrix}.$$

The **vector-real generalized force** of this rigid body at pole N is defined:

$$(35) \quad \mathbf{Q}_N = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{M}_N \end{bmatrix}.$$

The relationship between these two vectors is realized by the equality:

$$(36) \quad \mathbf{Q}_N = \mathbf{Q}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{Q}_O.$$

The vector \mathbf{Q}_N could be defined by other way.

Let a fixed number of active forces \mathbf{F}_k act on the rigid body, applied at points D_k , ($k=1,2,\dots,h$), and they are defined by radius vectors $\boldsymbol{\rho}_k$, (Fig.1).

The possible power of these forces, caused by a possible infinitely small change of the rigid body real generalized velocity, is determined:

$$\begin{aligned}
(37) \quad \delta P &= \sum_{k=1}^h \mathbf{F}_k^T \cdot \delta \mathbf{v}_k = \mathbf{F}^T \cdot \delta \mathbf{v}_o + (\mathbf{M}_o + \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o \cdot \mathbf{F})^T \cdot \delta \boldsymbol{\omega} = \\
&= \delta \mathbf{v}_o^T \cdot \mathbf{F} + \delta \boldsymbol{\omega}^T \cdot (\mathbf{M}_o + \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o \cdot \mathbf{F}) = \delta \langle \mathbf{v}_o^T \quad \boldsymbol{\omega}^T \rangle \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{M}_o + \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o \cdot \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix} = \\
&= \delta \langle \mathbf{v}_o \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} \rangle^T \cdot \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{M}_o \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{M}_o \end{bmatrix} \right) = \\
&= \delta \mathbf{u}_o^T \cdot (\mathbf{Q}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{Q}_o) .
\end{aligned}$$

Then the vector-*real* generalized forces of the rigid body at pole N will be:

$$\begin{aligned}
(38) \quad \mathbf{Q}_N &= \frac{\delta P}{\delta \mathbf{u}_o} = \frac{\delta \mathbf{u}_o^T}{\delta \mathbf{u}_o} \cdot (\mathbf{Q}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{Q}_o) = \bar{\mathbf{E}} \cdot (\mathbf{Q}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{Q}_o) = \\
&= \mathbf{Q}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{Q}_o , \quad \text{where}
\end{aligned}$$

$$(39) \quad \bar{\mathbf{E}} = \mathbf{diag} [1]_6 .$$

So, the most important Kinetics characteristics in the vector-matrix form are defined. They are necessary to introduce a new theorem, which is described in the next paragraph.

3. THEOREM OF CHANGE THE RIGID BODY GENERALIZED IMPULSE

The theorem states: *The first time derivative of the rigid body generalized impulse for a fixed pole is equal to its **real** generalized force determined for that pole.*

The mathematical record of the stated above theorem has the form:

$$(40) \quad \frac{d \mathbf{D}_N}{dt} = \mathbf{Q}_N .$$

Formulas (29) and (36) are substituted in equation (40) and it get the following kind :

$$(41) \quad \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{A}_o \cdot \mathbf{u}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{A}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_c) = \mathbf{Q}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{Q}_o .$$

The time derivative in equation (41) is performed:

$$(42) \quad \mathbf{A}_o \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_o + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_o \cdot \mathbf{u}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_c + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_c + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{A}_c \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_c = \mathbf{Q}_o + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{Q}_o .$$

The following detailed calculations are done below:

$$(43) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_c \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_c \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{J}_c \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(44) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{A}_c \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_c \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{v}}_c \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_c \\ \mathbf{J}_c \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_o \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_c \end{bmatrix} .$$

Taking into account the equations (43) and (44), equation (42) is simplified to the following type:

$$(45) \quad \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_O + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O + \ddot{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Q}_O + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O \cdot \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Now, the theorem of the mass center motion is used:

$$(46) \quad \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C = \mathbf{F}.$$

Through this theorem equation (45) takes the following form:

$$(47) \quad \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_O + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O = \mathbf{Q}_O - \ddot{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C.$$

So, the equation (47) represents the Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse at the fixed pole N .

Now, the same theorem, but to the moving pole O will be applied. For this purpose, a following vector is introduced:

$$(48) \quad \mathbf{Q}_O^* = \mathbf{Q}_O - \ddot{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C.$$

This vector is called **vector-real kinetic generalized force**.

Through this introduced new vector, equation (47) is recorded as follows:

$$(49) \quad \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_O + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O = \mathbf{Q}_O^*.$$

The above equation can be written even shorter, namely:

$$(50) \quad \frac{d \mathbf{D}_O}{dt} = \mathbf{Q}_O^*.$$

The equation (50) is performed the Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse but applied to the moving pole O . This variant of the theorem speaks that way: *The first time derivative of the rigid body generalized impulse for a movable pole is equal to its real kinetic generalized force determined for that pole.*

Let us assume the pole O coincides with the mass center C . Then equations (47), (48) and (50) takes the form:

$$(51) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C = \mathbf{Q}_C - \ddot{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C,$$

$$(52) \quad \mathbf{Q}_C^* = \mathbf{Q}_C - \ddot{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C,$$

$$(53) \quad \frac{d \mathbf{D}_C}{dt} = \mathbf{Q}_C^*.$$

Let us develop in detail the following vector-matrix product:

$$(54) \quad \begin{aligned} \ddot{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_C \\ \mathbf{J}_C \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

Now the equations (51), (52) and (53) take the following form:

$$(55) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C = \mathbf{Q}_C ,$$

$$(56) \quad \mathbf{Q}_C^* = \mathbf{Q}_C ,$$

$$(57) \quad \frac{d \mathbf{D}_C}{dt} = \mathbf{Q}_C .$$

Equation (57) performs the Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse for the pole O , which coincides with the mass center C . This variant of the theorem speaks that way: *The first time derivative of the rigid body generalized impulse for the body mass center is equal to its **real** generalized force determined for that center.*

It is obvious that this Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse, written by equation (40), (50) and (57), has the same structure.

4. CONDENSED LAGRANGE EQUATIONS

The following Condensed Lagrange equations are defined:

$$(58) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{\partial (E_k + \tilde{E})}{\partial \mathbf{u}_O} \right] = \mathbf{Q}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{Q}_O .$$

The scalar quantity is constructed in the following way:

$$(59) \quad \tilde{E} = \mathbf{u}_O^T \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{F}} ,$$

$$(60) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{D}_C = \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C .$$

Formulas (31) and (59) in equations (58) are substituted:

$$(61) \quad \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{A}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O) + \frac{d \tilde{\mathbf{F}}}{dt} = \mathbf{Q}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{Q}_O ,$$

$$(62) \quad \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{A}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O) + \frac{d}{dt} (\bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C) = \mathbf{Q}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{Q}_O ,$$

$$(63) \quad \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_O + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O + \dot{\bar{\mathbf{T}}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C = \mathbf{Q}_O + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{Q}_O .$$

The following detailed calculations are made:

$$(64) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_C \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(65) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \end{bmatrix} .$$

Given equations (64) and (65), equation (63) takes the following form:

$$(66) \quad \mathbf{A}_O \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_O + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_O \cdot \mathbf{u}_O + \dot{\bar{\mathbf{T}}}_O \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Q}_O + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_O \cdot \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix} .$$

The equation (66) is fully coincides with the equations (45) but now it is obtained by the other way.

Now, the Condensed Lagrange equations, but with the pole O , which is coincided with the mass center C will be applied. For this purpose, the equation (58) will be wrote in the following type:

$$(67) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{\partial (E_k + \tilde{E})}{\partial \mathbf{u}_C} \right] = \mathbf{Q}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{Q}_C .$$

The scalar \tilde{E} is constructed in the following way:

$$(68) \quad \tilde{E} = \mathbf{u}_C^T \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{F}} , \quad \text{where}$$

$$(69) \quad \tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{D}_C = \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C .$$

Formulas (33) and (68) in equations (67) are substituted and the following equation is obtained:

$$(70) \quad \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C) + \frac{d \tilde{\mathbf{F}}}{dt} = \mathbf{Q}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{Q}_C ,$$

$$(71) \quad \frac{d}{dt} (\mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C) + \frac{d}{dt} (\bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C) = \mathbf{Q}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{Q}_C ,$$

$$(72) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \dot{\bar{\mathbf{T}}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C = \mathbf{Q}_C + \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{Q}_C .$$

The following detailed calculations are performed:

$$(73) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{v}_C \\ \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{J}_C \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(74) \quad \bar{\mathbf{T}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_C \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(75) \quad \dot{\bar{\mathbf{T}}}_C \cdot \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \\ \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \\ = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_C \\ \mathbf{J}_C \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\tilde{\mathbf{R}}}_C \cdot \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} .$$

Taking into account the equality (73), (74) and (75), equation (72) is simplified to the following form:

$$(76) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_C \cdot \mathbf{M} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{v}}_C \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{Q}_C + \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \tilde{\mathbf{R}}_C \cdot \mathbf{F} \end{bmatrix} .$$

Through the Theorem of mass center motion, equation (76) takes the following simpler form:

$$(77) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C + \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C \cdot \mathbf{u}_C = \mathbf{Q}_C .$$

Equation (77) is fully coincides with the equation (55). Moreover, equation (77) can be obtained by the following type of Condensed Lagrange equation, namely:

$$(78) \quad \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{\partial E_k}{\partial \mathbf{u}_c} \right] = \mathbf{Q}_c .$$

Therefore the two forms of Condensed Lagrange equations from (67) and (78) lead to the same differential equation, namely equation (77). Or in other words, differential equation (77) can be obtained successfully by using of Condensed Lagrange equations from (67) or by using of Condensed Lagrange equations from (78).

5. DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

First, the variant when the pole O do not coincide with the mass center C will be developed. The time derivative of matrix \mathbf{A}_o is performed and the following expressions are obtained:

$$(79) \quad \dot{\mathbf{A}}_o = \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_o - \mathbf{B}_o \cdot \mathbf{\Phi} , \quad \text{where}$$

$$(80) \quad \mathbf{\Phi} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\Omega} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{\Omega} \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(81) \quad \mathbf{\Omega} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\omega_z & \omega_y \\ \omega_z & 0 & -\omega_x \\ -\omega_y & \omega_x & 0 \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(82) \quad \mathbf{B}_o = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & -\mathbf{S}_c^T \\ \mathbf{S}_c & \mathbf{J}_o \end{bmatrix} .$$

The formula (79) in equation (47) is substituted and then the following equation is obtained:

$$(83) \quad \mathbf{A}_o \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_o = \left(\mathbf{B}_o \cdot \mathbf{\Phi} - \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_o \right) \cdot \mathbf{u}_o + \mathbf{Q}_o - \dot{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{A}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_c .$$

Equation (83) is a vector-matrix record of a non-linear system of six differential equations describing the absolute general motion of a free asymmetric ideal rigid body at arbitrary chosen pole O .

Now, the following links are used:

$$(84) \quad \mathbf{u}_c = \mathbf{K}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_o , \quad \text{where}$$

$$(85) \quad \mathbf{K}_c = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} & \mathbf{R}_c^T \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{E} \end{bmatrix} .$$

The formula (84) is substituted in equation (83) and the following equation is obtained:

$$(86) \quad \mathbf{A}_o \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_o = \left(\mathbf{B}_o \cdot \mathbf{\Phi} - \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_o \right) \cdot \mathbf{u}_o + \mathbf{Q}_o - \dot{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{A}_c \cdot \mathbf{K}_c \cdot \mathbf{u}_o .$$

Finally, the formula (6) is substituted in the above equation and it is reached to the equation:

$$(87) \quad \mathbf{A}_o \cdot \left(\mathbf{H} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{H}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}} \right) = \left(\mathbf{B}_o \cdot \mathbf{\Phi} - \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_o \right) \cdot \mathbf{H} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{Q}_o - \dot{\mathbf{T}}_o \cdot \mathbf{A}_c \cdot \mathbf{K}_c \cdot \mathbf{H} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}} , \quad \text{where}$$

$$(88) \quad \dot{\mathbf{T}}_o = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \dot{\mathbf{R}}_o & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} ,$$

$$(89) \quad \dot{\mathbf{R}}_O = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\dot{\xi}_O & \dot{\eta}_O \\ \dot{\xi}_O & 0 & -\dot{\xi}_O \\ -\dot{\eta}_O & \dot{\xi}_O & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

After numerical integration of the differential equation (87) the law of absolute general motion of a free asymmetrical ideal rigid body at arbitrary chosen pole O will be found.

Now, the variant when the pole O coincides with the mass center C will be developed. The time derivative of matrix \mathbf{A}_C is performed and the following expression is obtained:

$$(90) \quad \dot{\mathbf{A}}_C = \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_C - \mathbf{B}_C \cdot \mathbf{\Phi}, \quad \text{where}$$

$$(91) \quad \mathbf{B}_C = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{J}_C \end{bmatrix}.$$

The formula (90) is substituted in equations (55) or (77) and the following equation is obtained:

$$(92) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot \dot{\mathbf{u}}_C = (\mathbf{B}_C \cdot \mathbf{\Phi} - \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_C) \cdot \mathbf{u}_C + \mathbf{Q}_C.$$

Equation (92) is a vector-matrix record of a non-linear system of six differential equations describing the absolute general motion of a free asymmetric ideal rigid body when the chosen pole O coincides with the mass center C .

In this case, the relation (6) is transformed to the following equation:

$$(93) \quad \mathbf{u}_C = \mathbf{H} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}.$$

The formula (93) is substituted in equation (92) and the finally equation is obtained:

$$(94) \quad \mathbf{A}_C \cdot (\mathbf{H} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \dot{\mathbf{H}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}}) = (\mathbf{B}_C \cdot \mathbf{\Phi} - \mathbf{\Phi} \cdot \mathbf{B}_C) \cdot \mathbf{H} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{Q}_C.$$

Differential equation (94) is very convenient for numerical integration.

6. CONCLUSION

Some new kinetic characteristics have been introduced. The main important are the **vector-real generalized velocity** and the **vector-generalized impulse** for an ideal rigid body.

A new theorem, called **Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse** for the fixed pole N or for the movable pole O (or C) is defined. It is applied to study the absolute general motion of a free asymmetric ideal rigid body.

The stated theorem is formulated directly. Nevertheless, it represents a summary of the two main theorems in Dynamics: Theorem of change of the quantity of motion and Theorem of change the kinetic moment, applied to an asymmetrical ideal rigid body that performs an absolute general motion. But directly defining of the new theorem became possible thanks to introducing the new kinetics characteristics and using the matrix operations.

New equations, called **Condensed Lagrange equation**, have been formulated. This equation leads to the same result as the Theorem of change the rigid body generalized impulse.

The obtained system of nonlinear differential equations in matrix form is convenient for a numerically integrating by the contemporary mathematical programs which is projected to use matrices and matrix calculations, for example MatLab, MathCAD, MuPAD and so on.

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